

Two stage collision: exploring the birth of Pangea in the Variscan terranes

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The Variscan suture contains a stack of terranes including two allochthonous units with continental affinity and Gondwanan provenance (Upper and Basal units; Fernández Suárez et al. 2003; Díez Fernández et al. 2012), separated by an ophiolite belt where the most common units show protoliths ages at c. 395 Ma (Díaz García et al. 1999; Arenas et al. 2007; Sánchez Martínez et al. 2007). The Upper units recorded a first high-P - ultra-high-P metamorphic event that occurred before 400-390 Ma (Fernández Suárez et al. 2007), while the Basal units were affected by a second high-P - low-to-intermediate-T metamorphic event dated at c. 370 Ma (Abati et al. 2010). Recent Lu-Hf zircon data obtained in the Early Devonian ophiolites show an interaction between an old continental crust and the gabbroic magmas, which consequently could not have originated in open oceanic domains (Sánchez Martínez et al. 2011; Arenas et al. 2014).

The tectonothermal evolution of the terranes with continental affinity records two consecutive events of deep subduction affecting the most external margin of Gondwana, developed in a context of dextral convergence with Laurussia. The development of the two high-P events alternated with the opening of a rather ephemeral oceanic basin, probably of pull-apart type, in Early Devonian times. This ephemeral oceanic domain is suggested as the setting for the protoliths of the most common ophiolites involved in the Variscan suture. Current ideas for the assembly of Pangea advocate for a single collision event between Gondwana and Laurussia, that occurred in Carboniferous times. However, the new evidences found in the allochthonous terranes of the Variscan belt seem to indicate a more complex scenario for the assembly of the supercontinent, with an interaction between the colliding continental margins that started

earlier and lasted longer than previously considered. Taking into account modern analogues of interaction between continents (García Casco et al. 2008), the development of complex collisions, as herein suggested for Gondwana and Laurussia during the assembly of Pangea, seems to be the norm rather than the exception throughout Earth history.

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